

Claisen Rearrangement of 2'-Hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'-prenyloxychalcone

AZIZUL ISLAM*, M. RAFIQUK ANAM and M. AMZAD HOSSAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

Manuscript received 3 December 1992, revised 12 May 1993, accepted 31 May 1993

Although much work has been reported on the Claisen rearrangement of 3-methylbut-2-enyl ether of xanthenes and coumarins and related compounds^{1,2}, such studies on flavonoids appear to have received little attention. Recently, the Claisen rearrangement of flavones, chalcones and related compounds has been reported³. Though the formation of abnormal rearrangement products is reported in other systems¹, like xanthenes and coumarins, no such products are formed from flavonoids. The chalcone (2) used for the Claisen rearrangement was obtained by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-4-prenyloxyacetophenone⁴ (1) with piperonal under alkaline condition. β -Resacetophenone when refluxed with prenyl bromide⁵ in presence of K_2CO_3 in acetone gave 2-hydroxy-4-prenyloxyacetophenone (1). We report herein our results of the Claisen rearrangement of chalcone (2) with Ac_2O in *N,N*-dimethylaniline and mild alkaline hydrolysis of the isolated products 4 and 5 (Scheme 1). The isolation of the major products by chromatographic technique and the characterisation of the products are also reported.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Gallenkamp electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 IR spectrophotometer, nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer with TMS as an internal standard and uv spectra (MeOH) on a Shimadzu UV-180 Ultraspek spectrophotometer. Tlc was performed

with silica gel 60G. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for all the compounds and the structures are in accord with the spectral data.

Scheme 1

2'-Hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'-prenyloxychalcone (2) : Alcoholic KOH (2.8 g in 12 ml MeOH) was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-4-prenyloxyacetophenone⁴ (1; 2.5 g) and piperonal (1.82 g) in ethanol (40 ml). The solution was kept at room temperature for 48 h. It was then diluted with ice-cold water, acidified with cold dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The ether layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and

evaporated to dryness. Crystallisation of the crude mass from ethanol gave yellow needles (2.4 g), m.p. 120° (Found : C, 71.73; H, 5.91. $C_{21}H_{20}O_5$ requires : C, 71.58; H, 5.69%); R_f 0.78 (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate; 4 : 1); it gave brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; λ_{max} 220, 225 and 320 nm; ν_{max} 3450, 1630, 1040 and 925 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(CDCl_3)$ 1.74 (6H, s, $C(CH_3)_2$), 4.53 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH=$), 5.48 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH=$), 6.02 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.45 (2H, dd, J 2.5 and 9 Hz, H-3' and 5'), 7.12 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.45 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.78 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 8.01 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β) and 12.05 (1H, s, OH).

Claisen rearrangement of 2'-hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'-prenyloxychalcone (2) : Oxygen-free nitrogen was passed for 2 h through a solution of the chalcone (2; 1.5 g) in freshly distilled *N,N*-dimethylaniline (10 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml) contained in a heavy-walled glass tube. The tube was carefully sealed and immersed in an oil-bath at $185 \pm 5^\circ$ for 4 h. The mixture was diluted with ice-cold water (150 ml), set aside for 2 h and then extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate layer was treated with dilute HCl (1%, w/v) to get pH 2 of the solution followed by aqueous K_2CO_3 (5%, w/v) to pH 11 and finally with brine to neutrality. The organic layer was dried and evaporated to a crude mass. Fractionation of the crude mass over silica gel using petroleum ether, petroleum ether-benzene (10 : 1), petroleum ether-benzene (10 : 3), petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) successively as eluents gave six major compounds A-F.

Compound-A crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether gave the starting chalcone (2; 70 mg), (co-tlc and m.m.p.). *Compound-B* was crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles (105 mg), m.p. 105° (Found : C, 71.70 ; H, 5.85. $C_{21}H_{20}O_5$ requires : C, 71.59; H, 5.68%); R_f 0.87 (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate; 4 : 1); λ_{max} 225 and 327 nm; ν_{max} 3420, 1642, 1030 and 930 cm^{-1} ;

$\delta(CDCl_3)$ 1.32 and 1.39 (6H, 2s, $2 \times CH_3$ at C-4''), 1.40 (3H, d, 7 Hz, CH_3 at C-5''), 4.45 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, H-5''), 6.01 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.48 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.18 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.45 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.72 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 8.03(1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β) and 13.01 (1H, s, OH). It was identified as 2'-hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'',4'',5''-trimethyl-dihydrofurano(2'',3'' : 4',3')chalcone (3). *Compound-C* isolated fraction from column was purified by preparative tlc over silica gel 60G using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as developing solvent. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as orange needles (225 mg), m.p. 109° (Found : C, 70.23; H, 5.75. $C_{23}H_{22}O_6$ requires : C, 70.04; H, 5.57%); R_f 0.74 (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate; 4 : 1); λ_{max} 320 nm; ν_{max} 3430, 1760, 1645, 1040 and 930 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(CDCl_3)$ 1.49 (6H, s, $C(CH_3)_2$), 2.21 (3H, s, 4'- $COCH_3$), 4.82 (2H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_B and H_C), 6.02 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.21 (1H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_A), 6.47 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.15 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.48 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.78 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 8.00 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β), 13.01 (1H, s, OH). It was identified as 2'-hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'-acetoxy-3'-(α,α -dimethylallyl)chalcone (4). *Compound-D* obtained from column was purified by preparative tlc over silica gel 60G using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as developing solvent. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as yellow needles (55 mg), m.p. 134° (Found : C, 70.21; H, 5.83. $C_{23}H_{22}O_6$ requires : C, 70.05; H, 5.59%); R_f 0.64 (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate; 4 : 1); λ_{max} 325 nm; ν_{max} 3445, 1760, 1645, 1040 and 930 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(CDCl_3)$ 1.54 (6H, s, $C(CH_3)_2$), 2.23 (3H, s, 4'- $COCH_3$), 4.98 (2H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_B and H_C), 6.00 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.23 (1H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_A), 6.38 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.08 (3H, m, H-2,5 and 6), 7.49 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.68 (1H, s, H-6'), 7.94 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β), 12.75 (1H, s, OH). It was identified as 2'-hydroxy-3, 4-methylenedioxy-4'-acetoxy-5'-(α,α -dimethylallyl) chalcone (5). *Compound-E* isolated fraction from column was purified

by preparative tlc over silica gel 60G using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as developing solvent. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as yellow crystals (105 mg), m.p. 95–96° (Found : C, 70.35; H, 5.85. $C_{23}H_{22}O_6$ requires : C, 70.04; H, 5.58%); R_f 0.52 (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate; 4 : 1); λ_{max} 220, 250 and 325 nm; ν_{max} 1760, 1640, 1040 and 925 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.73 (6H, s, $C(CH_3)_2$), 2.25 (3H, s, 2'-COCH₃), 4.53 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH=$), 5.46 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH=$), 6.01 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.43 (2H, dd, J 2.5 and 9 Hz, H-3' and 5'), 7.12 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.40 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.71 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 8.03 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β). It was identified as 2'-acetoxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'-prenyloxychalcone (6). Compound-F obtained from column was purified by preparative tlc over silica gel 60G using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as developing solvent. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as yellow crystals (81 mg), m.p. 147° (Found : C, 66.53; H, 4.51. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 66.25; H, 4.29%); R_f 0.47 (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate; 4 : 1); λ_{max} 320 nm; ν_{max} 3420, 1760, 1645, 1030 and 925 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.24 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 6.01 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.47 (2H, dd, J 2.5 and 9 Hz, H-3' and 5'), 7.10 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.43 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.74 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 8.03 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β), 13.05 (1H, s, OH). It was identified as 2'-hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-4'-acetoxychalcone (7).

Hydrolysis of 4 to 2',4'-dihydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-3'-(α,α -dimethylallyl)chalcone (8) : The acetate (4; 250 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) with gentle heating. NaOH in ethanol (1%, w/v; 5 ml) was added it and the mixture was warmed on a steam-bath for 1 min until the orange red colour changed to yellow. The solution was then neutralised with dilute HCl (1%, w/v) and extracted with ethyl acetate. The usual work-up gave a crude product which on separation by preparative tlc over silica gel 60G using petroleum ether-benzene-acetone

(15 : 4 : 3) as developing solvent gave the hydrolysis product. The product was crystallised from benzene-ethyl acetate as yellow needles (180 mg), m.p. 125–26° (Found : C, 71.81; H, 5.94. $C_{21}H_{20}O_5$ requires : C, 71.58; H, 5.59%); R_f 0.68 (petroleum ether-benzene-acetone, 15 : 4 : 3); λ_{max} 225, 250 and 320 nm; ν_{max} 3450, 1645, 1040 and 930 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.63 (6H, s, $C(CH_3)_2$), 4.82 (2H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_B and H_C), 6.00 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.25 (1H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_A), 6.48 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.18 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.45 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.68 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 8.03 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β), 12.75 (1H, s, OH).

Hydrolysis of 5 to 2',4'-dihydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-5'-(α,α -dimethylallyl)chalcone (9) : Hydrolysis of 5 (50 mg) was carried out as described above. The reaction product on purification by preparative tlc over silica gel 60G using benzene-acetone (9 : 10) as developing solvent and crystallisation from benzene afforded 9 as yellow crystals (28 mg), m.p. 112° (Found : C, 71.81; H, 5.83. $C_{21}H_{20}O_5$ requires : C, 71.59; H, 5.58%); R_f 0.66 (benzene-acetone, 9 : 1); λ_{max} 222 and 325 nm; ν_{max} 3455, 1640, 1030 and 925 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.72 (6H, s, $C(CH_3)_2$), 5.20 (2H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_B and H_C), 6.02 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.25 (1H, dd, J 10 and 18 Hz, H_C), 6.44 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.18 (3H, m, H-2, 5 and 6), 7.42 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- α), 7.62 (1H, s, H-6'), 7.98 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H- β), 13.25 (1H, s, OH).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. A. J. Miah, Department of Chemistry, University of Waterloo, Canada, for his help in connection with nmr spectroscopy, and are also grateful to Mr. Saidur Rahman, Department of Chemistry, University of Glasgow, U.K. for elemental analysis. One of the authors (M.R.A.) is grateful to University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh, for providing a Fellowship.

References

1. H. D. LOCKSLEY, J. QUILLINAN and F. SCHEINMANN, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1971, 3804; E. O. BURLING, A. JEFFERSON and F. SCHEINMANN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, **21**, 2653; A. DYER, A. JEFFERSON and F. SCHEINMANN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 1559; A. C. JAIN and S. M. ANAND, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1974, 329; H. D. LOCKSLEY, A. J. QUILLINANA and F. S. CHEINMANN, *Chem. Commun.*, 1969, 1505; M. M. BALLANTYNE, R. D. H. MURRAY and A. B. PENROSE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, **39**, 4155; R. D. H. MURRAY and M. M. BALLANTYNE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, **26**, 5667; R. D. H. MURRAY, M. M. BALLANTYNE, T. C. HAGG and P. H. MCCABBE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, **31**, 2960; S. MAHEY, T. R. SESHADRI and S. K. MUKERJEE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 292.
2. A. C. JAIN and S. M. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 971.
3. A. C. JAIN and D. K. TULI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, **47**, 682; A. C. JAIN, D. K. TULI and R. KHAZANCHI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978 **16**, 973; A. ISLAM and M. KRISHNAMURTHI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 1037.
4. A. C. JAIN, PYARELAL and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 1072.
5. H. STAUDINGER, W. KREIS and W. SCHLET, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 75.